

Uncovering Hidden Learning Dynamics in Deep Learning Models for Alzheimer's and MCI MRI Using Statistical Complexity

Seyi Olabisi Omotoso¹ and Luiz Otavio Murta Jr.^{1,2}

¹*Department of Physics and* ²*Department of Computing and Mathematics of the Faculty of Philosophy, Sciences, and Letters of Ribeirão Preto, University of Sao Paulo*

seyitoso@usp.br

The diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease, MCI and dementia presents a critical challenge, as these neurodegenerative conditions often involve subtle brain changes that conventional imaging methods fail to detect. Traditional metrics such as loss and entropy capture error and uncertainty but don't uncover the deeper, intricate patterns within MRI data. These limitations restrict early detection and accurate diagnosis, necessitating advanced computational techniques. This study introduces a novel metric that identifies subtle brain patterns, enhancing the understanding of dementia. This metric is called statistical complexity.

Using DenseNet-121 and EfficientNet-B1, the dataset was partitioned into ten subsets ranging from 10% to 100% in 10% increments to examine how statistical complexity evolves with increasing data availability. Synaptic weights were extracted from each model and transformed into probability distributions, from which entropy and disequilibrium were computed. Statistical complexity was then obtained as the product of entropy and disequilibrium, following the definition of LMC complexity.

Results showed that statistical complexity increases with dataset size. Smaller datasets exhibited an irregular (zigzag) pattern in training loss and statistical complexity, indicating overfitting. Larger datasets demonstrated smoother patterns, suggesting better model learning. Using the full dataset, a layer-by-layer analysis revealed distinct architectural signatures. DenseNet-121 exhibited increasing complexity in deeper layers—particularly in `denseblock3`, `norm5`, and `transition3`—indicating progressive refinement of high-level neuroanatomical features, while early layers such as `conv0` and `denseblock2` showed reduced complexity. In contrast, EfficientNet-B1 displayed fluctuating complexity in early layers and consistent declines in mid-layers, stabilizing only at the final layer, suggesting weaker hierarchical feature organization compared to DenseNet-121.

These findings confirm that statistical complexity is a reliable metric for assessing model performance in Alzheimer's disease classification and may provide more nuanced insights into model training dynamics. This approach has the potential to significantly improve early diagnosis and model reliability in clinical settings.